

The Effects of Multicultural-Based School Management and Teachers' Characters on Students' Characters in Catholic Schools in the Provinces of Bali and West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p data-bbox="199 533 368 560"><i>Article History</i></p> <p data-bbox="199 595 360 651">Received: April 16, 2021</p> <p data-bbox="199 687 360 743">Accepted: June 22, 2021</p> <p data-bbox="199 779 472 898">Keywords: Management, Multicultural, Character, Teachers, Students.</p>	<p data-bbox="560 533 1402 1140"><i>Teachers' characters (TC) and students' characters (SC) are important parts of the education system that can integrate multicultural values through multicultural-based school management (MBSM). Weak commitment, loose policies, teacher unpreparedness, and diversity of student backgrounds are problems faced by all schools including catholic schools. The purpose of this study was to determine the causal relationship of the variable multicultural-based school management and teachers' characters on students' characters in catholic schools in the Provinces of Bali and West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia. This research, which used a quantitative approach, involved 160 teachers in Bali and West Nusa Tenggara Provinces, Indonesia. Descriptive analysis was used to describe the relationship between variables and SEM (Structure Equation Model) and also used to examine the hypotheses. The results of the descriptive analysis showed that MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters according to teacher perceptions were in the category of good and the results of hypotheses test showed that there were a significant effects of MBSM on teachers' characters, MBSM on students' characters, teachers' characters on students' characters, a significant indirect effect of MBSM on students' characters through teachers' characters and a significant effect of MBSM and teachers' characters on students' characters simultaneously.</i></p>
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Introduction

Teachers' characters and students' characters play an important role in building the nation's characters. Instilling the value of diversity, justice, and equality through multicultural-based governance can create human resources with positive characteristics so that they will be able to face challenges in life. Character is a core moral value obtained by understanding care and action so that a person can live harmoniously and productively (Lickona, 2013). Thus, character education especially multicultural values need to be taught gradually from the playgroup (Nikawanti, 2017) to elementary school (Sutjipto et al., 2017) to junior high school (Pertwi & Marsigit, 2017) and finally to high school (Ariana et al., 2020).

The erosion of multicultural values causes social conflicts in many parts of the world due to differences of skin color, ethnicity, and religion (Assifa, 2019). The diversity issues such as bullying of minority students due to differences in religion, ethnicity, or race, to the notion of radicalism (Auliani, 2019) have penetrated the world of education. Therefore, the Indonesian government issued Presidential decree Number 87 of 2017 concerning character education as an effort to strengthen the nation's characters. In this case, the teachers play an important role in shaping students' characters (Lickona, 1997). Precise pedagogy (Cooley, 2008) allows students to have moral values to build their self-identity to become individuals who are capable to interact in society (Pattaro, 2016). There are several obstacles faced in implementing multicultural values at schools including (1) The government does not develop vivid aims of multicultural education that can integrate all components in the school to teach students multiculturalism (Raihani, 2018), (2) Teachers do not understand the concept and are not dedicated enough to teach multicultural values to students (Hoon, 2013), and (3) The curriculum contents do not provide sufficient space to teach multicultural values (Listia & Lian, 2007).

Those various obstacles illustrate that the management related to multicultural values is poor. To answer this problem, according to Fiedler & Chemers (1974), the management needs to adjust to the situational needs to be more effective. Multicultural-Based School Management (MBSM) is educational governance that integrates multicultural values with all management activities, personnel performance, educational services, and learning activities at schools (Banks, 2009; Gorski, 2010). Through planning, organization, leadership, control and clear delegation (Robin, 2013). The more people participating and contributing, the more effective it will be to achieve the goals that have been set (Hawkins & James, 2017) that ultimately they can give a contribution to

schools, students, and society (Keskin, 2018). This is in line with the opinion (Hoover, 2003) that the success of character building in education at schools is determined not by the strength of the learning process but by its management.

Internalization of character values to students cannot be achieved without a systematic and gradual educational process (Irvine & Armento, 2001). Therefore, multicultural-based learning integrated into the curriculum can foster the character of equality and justice and reduce students' prejudice. In this case, the role of teachers is very strategic because, in leadership, the multicultural learning task is associated with teachers' competence, especially social and professional competence (Rochana et al., 2018). Meanwhile, teachers' character values can be developed through multicultural awareness that is influenced by their past experiences (Russell & Russell, 2014), environment (Jackson, 2014), and cultural empathy, flexibility, and emotional balance (Hanafi et al., 2020). To build students' and teachers' characters effectively, multicultural-based school management needs to be practiced systematically so that teachers and students respect differences, become tolerant, and love peace (Nakaya, 2018). The implementation of MBSM is constrained by the weak commitment and the teachers' characters as well as the uncertainty of government policies (Raihani, 2018). An effective multicultural-based school management model is needed to increase teacher commitment and competence and convince the government to be more assertive in implementing policies on multicultural education.

Multicultural values contained in article 1 of *Gravissimum Educationis* (GE) document, stating that the church through education highly respects and recognizes the right of everyone to education, regardless of cultural, religious, ethnic, and ethnic differences (Paul VI, 1965; CCE, 2013), has been made the basis of character education in Catholic schools around the world, including Indonesia. The fact is that, in Catholic schools, character values have also begun to erode because there are still many obstacles faced in implementing multicultural values. This research was conducted in Catholic schools in Bali and West Nusa Tenggara. Socioculturally, schools in these two areas are interesting to study because of their communities. Balinese culture is influenced by Hinduism (Vickers, 2012) and West Nusa Tenggara which majority is Muslim, is influenced by Balinese culture (Amin, 1997). Several social conflicts triggered by ethnic and religious issues that occurred in this area illustrate that there are issues related to diversity, tolerance, equality, and justice.

Schools as one of the educational institutions that play a role in preparing human resources need to apply multicultural values in all aspects of its management to develop human resources with positive characteristics. Multicultural values such as justice, equality, and tolerance foster an open attitude for students to collaborate with more people in facing global challenges. Studies on multicultural education and character education have been carried out qualitatively in previous research studies, however research on multicultural-based school management and studies on the relationship between MBSM and teachers' characters with students' characters quantitatively have never been carried out and reported. This is important to do to measure the effect of MBSM in education governance so that MBSM as an important variable in education management can theoretically be understood more objectively and practically effectively to improve the character of teachers and the character of students in schools. Therefore, the objectives of this study are: 1) To find out the effect of MBSM on teachers' characters (TC); 2) To find out the effect of MBSM on students' characters (SC); 3) To find out the effect of teachers' characters (TC) on students' characters (SC); 4) To find out the indirect effect of MBSM on students' characters (SC) through teachers' characters (TC) and 5) To find out the effects of MBSM and Teachers' characters (TC) on Students' characters (SC) simultaneously.

Literature Review

School management is an effort to manage education in schools to achieve predetermined goals through planning, organization, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation in all activities namely school management, personnel performance, educational service performance, and learning (Robin, 2013). Meanwhile, multicultural education is a process of integrating multicultural values in education at school to develop equality and justice values (Banks, 2009; Gorski, 2010), to be responsive to culture and diversity (Rochana et al., 2018), equitable pedagogy, sociocultural teaching, and social justice (Sleeter, 2018). Thus, MBSM is an educational governance effort that emphasizes the internalization of multicultural values to develop equality and justice values in schools.

Teachers' characters are important and fundamental because teachers lead students to become individuals who possess positive moral values (O'Sullivan, 2004) manifested in the form of core ethical values or ideal behavior including knowledge, feelings, and actions which then become one's competence and quality (Lickona, 2013). Teachers have a central role in providing character education for students (Lickona, 1997) so that their personal and social competence should be inherent as stated in the Decree of the Minister of Education of the Republic of Indonesia Number 16 of 2007.

Students' characters is a virtue possessed by students through pedagogy (Cooley, 2008), behavior that becomes a reference for students to act, the ability to see different perspectives and be mature in difficult situations, welfare, moral values, and moral actions of students at school (Berkowitz & Hoppe, 2009) and the basis for

building student's identity (Pattaro, 2016). According to Lickona (2013), students' characters include knowledge, feelings, and actions, while in the Decree of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2018, the character is the embodiment of 5 main values namely religiosity, nationalism, independence, cooperation and integrity.

MBSM provides opportunities for teachers to live their character in collaborating with fellow teachers and students so that they can contribute to the achievement of the school's vision and mission (Russell & Russell, 2014). With good teachers' characters, schools will be able to solve problems in education related to different backgrounds of students (Arsal, 2019).

MBSM is a management activity that integrates multicultural values in all its aspects. If multicultural-based school management has been integrated into the curriculum and through a systematic and gradual process (Irvine & Armento, 2001), the students' characters such as the equality character, justice, and tolerance will develop (Özturgut, 2011) so that students respect differences, be tolerant and love peace (Nakaya, 2018).

Teachers have a big role in shaping students' characters at school because they can teach and provide good examples. Therefore, teachers' characters needs to be considered since they attended teacher training (McGraw & Fish, 2018). Good character taught and exemplified by the teachers can increase the effectiveness of character education (Lickona, 1997) and influence the improvement of students' characters (Toropova et al, 2019).

MBSM provides broad autonomy to schools in carrying out their programs according to their conditions (Kostis & Efthymia, 2009). One of the programs that can increase teacher awareness of multicultural character is training activities (Keskin, 2018). Effective school management can improve personal competence, social competence, and potential diversity (Hanafi et al., 2020) to enable the teachers to play their roles as teachers and role models of moral values to students (Banks, 2009). Thus, indirectly, effective MBSM and the role of teachers in teaching and modeling good character can improve students' characters, especially multicultural character (Banks, 2015) that helps students to be able to participate in a larger community.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses of this study are:

H1: There is a significant effect of MBSM on Teachers' Characters

H2: There is a significant effect of MBSM on Students' Characters

H3: There is a significant effect of Teachers' Characters on Students' Characters

H4: There is a significant indirect effect of MBSM on Students' Characters through Teachers' Characters

H5: There is a significant effect of MBSM and Teachers' Characters on Students' Characters simultaneously.

METHOD

Design and Variables of the Research

This study did not manipulate the variables under study, but took measurements in a natural setting, therefore the design was a non-experimental study. In accordance with the purpose of this study was to explain the dependence relationship between several variables in educational management in schools, the design of this study was not just a **co-relational study** as in Tuckman's sense (1999), but rather a **causal relationship study** as defined by Gall et al. (2003). That was, in terms of the nature of the relationship between variables, this study did not only explain the relationship, but more than that, it also explained the level of dependence between variables (Hair et al., 2014; Creswell, 2014; Solimun et al., 2017). MBSM was an exogenous variable where the indicators were management activities (MA), personal performance (PP), educational services (ES), and learning activities (LA), while teachers' characters and students' characters were endogenous variables where the indicators are knowledge (KN), feelings (FE), and actions (AC).

Population and Sample

This study involved 160 teachers as a sample which was drawn by the proportional stratified area random sampling technique using the Slovin formula. The population is 695 teachers in Catholic schools in Bali and West Nusa Tenggara Provinces, Indonesia. According to some experts, the number of samples that close to ideal for SEM analysis is 100 to 200 (Hair et al., 2014) because samples over 200 often cause the chi-square value too sensitive that the measure of Goodness of Fit is poor (Vandenberg, 2006). The sample distribution for each stratum was given in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of sample in each stratum

Stratum	Number of populations	Number of samples
Elementary School	338	77.81 is rounded to 78
Junior High School	192	44.20 is rounded to 44
Senior High School	165	37.98 is rounded to 38
Total	695	160

Research Instruments

A teacher perception questionnaire was used to measure the data of MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters. Each item in the questionnaire contained statement or questions followed by choices of answers that were made by using a Likert scale where the lowest score is 1 (one) which means a respondent strongly disagrees and the highest score is 5 (five) which means a respondent strongly agrees with positive statements and vice versa for negative statements (Hair et al., 2014). Descriptive data about the respondents' gender, ethnicity, religion, and teaching experience were also collected. The content validity of the instrument was tested by expert judgment and empirical validity was tested on 60 respondents. The results of the content validity analysis using Aiken's V formula showed that the V coefficient is greater than 0.3 for all items, meaning that the instrument has a good validity so that it can be used for research.

Table 2. Results of Analysis of Aiken's V

Aspect	Aiken's (V) Coefficient	Criteria
Relevance	0.771	Valid
Accuracy	0.729	Valid
Presentation	0.733	Valid
Language	0.784	Valid

The results of the empirical validity test using Pearson correlation analysis showed that two of the 64 items tested were invalid ($p > 0.05$). Furthermore, the results of the reliability test showed that the instrument had high reliability because the Cronbach alpha value was higher than 0.6 (Table 3) so that it can be used to measure MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters. Of the questions that have met the validity and reliability requirements, 35 items which consisted of 17 questions for the MBSM variable, 10 questions for the teachers' characters variable, and 8 questions for the character variable were selected.

Table 3. The result of the validity and reliability test of the instrument (N=60)

Variable	Significance Value (2tailed)	Number of Valid Items	Cronbach's Alpha Value	Criteria
MBSM	<0.05	24	0.916	Reliable
TC	<0.05	21	0.877	Reliable
SC	<0.05	17	0.817	Reliable

Data Analysis Technique

Data of MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters were collected using a questionnaire in the google form. The data were tabulated and analyzed descriptively using the average value of the frequency distribution and categorized according to the criteria in Table 4 (Solimun et al., 2017). Hypotheses were tested by using Structure Equation Model (Hair et al, 2014) with the help of AMOS 24 for the Windows program to obtain a fixed model.

Table 4. Category of Respondents Perception Based on the Average Value

Interval	Category
4,20 – 5,00	Very Good
3,40 – 4,19	Good
2,60 – 3,39	Satisfactory
1,80 – 2,59	Poor
1,00 – 1,79	Very poor

RESULTS

Results of Descriptive Analysis

Multiculturalism in terms of gender, ethnicity, religion, and teaching experience was used to describe the characteristics of respondents (Table 5). In general, the majority of respondents are female teachers (59.38%), Balinese (56.25%), the majority are Catholic

(65.63%) and had teaching experience of more than fifteen years (48.75%).

Table 5. Description of Respondents Characteristic

Aspect	Sub-aspect	N	Percentage (%)
Gender	a. Male	65	40.63
	b. Female	95	59.38
Ethnic	a. Balinese	90	56.25
	b. Sasak-Sumbawanese	10	6.25
	c. Java	37	23.13
	d. Flores	22	13.75
	e. Other	1	0.63
Religion	a. Catholic	105	65.63
	b. Protestant	7	4.38
	c. Hinduism	39	24.38
	d. Islam	9	5.63
Teaching Experience	a. < 5 year	18	11.25
	b. 5 -10 year	34	21.25
	c. 11-15 year	30	18.75
	d. > 15 year	78	48.75

The results of the analysis of the respondents' answers to the MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters variables were shown in a frequency distribution table containing average value and standard deviation (Table 6). Based on Table 6, it is seen that MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters were all categorized as good where the average value was 4.07 ± 0.74 , 4.00 ± 0.78 , and 3.74 ± 0.79 respectively.

Table 6. The Frequency Distribution of MBSM, Teachers' Characters and Students' Characters

VARIABLES	INDICATORS	1		2		3		4		5		Mean	SD
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
MBSM	MA	0	0%	2	8%	46	20%	58	25%	54	23%	4.02	0.81
	PP	0	0%	1	1%	33	15%	78	34%	48	21%	4.09	0.71
	ES	0	0%	0	0%	43	19%	53	23%	65	28%	4.13	0.81
	LA	0	0%	0	0%	31	13%	88	38%	41	18%	4.07	0.66
The average of MBSM variable											4.07	0.74	
TC	KN	0	0%	3	0%	35	21%	68	43%	54	36%	4.08	0.82
	FE	0	0%	8	4%	45	25%	60	39%	47	32%	3.94	0.81
	AC	0	0%	3	2%	44	25%	62	40%	51	33%	4.00	0.73
The average of Teachers' characters variable											4.00	0.78	
SC	KN	0	0%	23	10%	54	23%	60	26%	23	10%	3.53	0.79
	FE	0	0%	15	7%	35	15%	63	27%	47	20%	3.88	0.85
	AC	0	0%	11	5%	41	18%	74	32%	34	15%	3.83	0.73
The average of Students' Characters variable											3.74	0.79	

1=Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly Agree, f = Frequency

The Analysis Result of SEM

The data analysis stages of SEM to test hypothesis were:

- (1) Developing a theoretical model based on an established theory, assessing model constancy and consistency and the cause-effects correlation between factors developed as a conceptual model based on empirical data (Figure 1)

- (2) Developing a path diagram with parameter estimation of path analysis using AMOS software and the result is in Figure2.
- (3) Converting the path diagram to structural equation model for MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters. The conversion is in table 7.

Table 7. Structure Equation Model

Equation	R ²	Percentage (%)
TC = 0.959 MBSM	0.713	71.3%
SC = 0.261 MBSM + 0.559 TC	0.828	82.8%

Figure 2. Path Diagram for MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters variables.

- (4) All items for MBSM, teachers' characters, and students' characters were valid because the loading factor value was >0.5 and met the reliable requirement because the value of $CR > 0.7$ and $AVE > 0.5$. The normality result showed that all variables were normal because the value of CR was between -2.58 and 2.58 . The result of outlier test showed that the highest mahalanobis distance value was 29.610 and chi square value with significance = 0.001 was 32.909. Thus, the mahalanobis value $<$ chi square table. This means there was no outlier. Based on the multicollinearity test, it could be concluded that there was no multicollinearity because the correlation value of the three variables was < 0.9 .
- (5) The result of model fit test using goodness of fit test with ten parameters showed that the construct in the research model corresponded to the research data. The summary of goodness of fit test was in Table 8.

Table 8. Summary of Goodness of Fit (GOF) test result

Goodness of Fit	Cut off value	Results	Conclusion
Chi Square Probability	≥ 0.05	0,082	Fit
CMIN/DF	≤ 2.00	1,383	Fit
GFI	≥ 0.90	0,956	Fit
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0,916	Fit
CFI	≥ 0.90	0,992	Fit
TLI	≥ 0.90	0,988	Fit
NFI	≥ 0.90	0,972	Fit
IFI	≥ 0.90	0,992	Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0,049	Fit
RMR	≤ 0.05	0,011	Fit

(6) Hypothesis Testing

The significance of causal relationship in SEM analysis was tested using the null hypothesis showing that the coefficient of causal relationship between variables was null by using a t-test, commonly used in regression analysis. The summary of causal relationship between variables based on the SEM full analysis output is in Table 9.

Table 9. The Hypothesis Testing of Direct Effects

Variables	Estimation	S.E.	C.R.	t-table	P-Value	Conclusion
MBSM \rightarrow TC	0.959	0.081	11.802	1.960	0.000	Significant
MBSM \rightarrow SC	0.261	0.104	2.513	1.960	0.012	Significant
TC \rightarrow SC	0.559	0.109	5.109	1.960	0.000	Significant

H1: The Effect of MBSM on Teachers' Characters

Based on the summary of the SEM analysis result in Table 8, the *critical ratio* (CR) value of the effects of MBSM on teachers' characters was 11.802. It was higher than the t-table value (1.960), and the significance value was $0.000 < 0.05$. This result showed that MBSM affected teachers' characters. Thus, the first hypothesis: the significant effect of MBSM on teachers' characters, was acceptable.

H2: The Effect of MBSM on Students' Characters

The *critical ratio* (CR) value in Table 8 for the effects of MBSM on students' characters was 2.513 – higher than the t-table value (1.960) -, and the significance value was $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on this result, the causal relationship significance in the model was accepted. Thus, the second hypothesis: the significant effect of MBSM on students' characters, was acceptable.

H3: The Effect of Teachers Characters on Students' Characters

The SEM analysis results in Table 8 shows that the *critical ratio* (CR) value for the effects of teachers' characters on students' characters was 5.109 – higher than the t-table value (1.960) -, and the significance value was $0.000 < 0.05$. The result showed teachers' characters affected students' characters. Thus, the third hypothesis: The significant effect of teachers' characters on students' characters, was acceptable.

H4: The Effect of MBSM on Students' characters mediated by Teachers' Characters

The result of Sobel test on indirect effects from MBSM characters on students' characters through teachers' characters was presented in Table 10.

Table 10. The result of Hypothesis Testing of Indirect and Simultaneously Effects

Relationship	t-test	t-table	F-test	F-table	Conclusion
MBSM \rightarrow TC \rightarrow SC	4.692	1.960			Significant
SC \leftarrow MBSM, TC			377.895	3.05363	Significant

The Sobel test result showed the t-test value of MBSM on students' characters through teachers' characters was 4.692. It was higher than the t-table (1.960). Therefore, the fourth hypothesis: the significant indirect effect of MBSM on students' characters through teachers' characters, was acceptable.

H5: The Effect of MBSM and Teachers' Characters on Students' Characters simultaneously

The SEM analysis result in Table 10 showed that the F-test value of simultaneously effect of MBSM and teachers' characters on students' characters was 377.895. It was higher than F-table (3.05363). Therefore, the fifth hypothesis: the significant simultaneously effect of MBSM and teachers' characters on students' characters, was acceptable.

DISCUSSIONS

The results of this study reveal the direct effect of MBSM on teachers' characters, especially in the aspect of knowledge about multicultural values. Through well-managed education services, teachers gain knowledge about equality, justice, diversity and tolerance which will be applied in classroom learning. In the multicultural classroom, the teacher has an important role (Mubaraq et al., 2019) sehingga, so Banks emphasized that through school management that empowers the potential for diversity, it can make the teachers able to carry out their role as teachers and set an example of multicultural values for their students, so that students' multicultural values can increase (Banks, 2015). Therefore, Hoover (2003) that the success of the character building process at several levels of education is determined not by the strength of the learning process, but by the strength of its management. Russell & Russell (2014) views that MBSM is able to foster teacher awareness to see differences as a potential that has a positive impact in order to improve student achievement.

Besides influencing of teachers' characters, MBSM also has a significant effect on students' characters. The Feeling is one of the most sensitive students' character indicators, if linked to different religions and ethnicity (Lickona, 2013). This indicator is needed to be accommodated in a management system so that students and teachers could appreciate and tolerate differences and love peace (Nakaya, 2018). According to Vogt (1997) and Irvine & Armento (2001), the characters' values internalization cannot be attained without a systematic process. Curriculum integration can build character values such as equality and equity characters and decrease prejudice. Davis (2003) stated that students' character building has to depend on the condition and not be the standard for graduation. It has to be integrated into the teaching and learning process, for example: through a transformative Civics education (Nakaya, 2018). However, the implementation shall be consistent in changing the students' attitude to a better one significantly.

The significant effect of teachers' characters on students' characters in this finding reinforces the opinion that teachers have an important role in exemplifying multicultural values to their students. An individual character is shaped through a process of understanding (knowledge), care (feeling), and actions (Lickona, 2013), and teachers that can implement multicultural values well. Teachers can affect students' characters because their roles are significant in students' character building. The result of this study refuted Aurin & Maurer's arguments (1993), stating teachers' roles in character education at school were only qua external balancers. Teachers must determine the right strategy to manage social-moral conflicts in classes. Therefore, there is a need to pay more attention to their beliefs, teaching context, and personal backgrounds. A strict selection and screening process for teacher candidates is needed to get teachers with good character (McGraw & Fish, 2018).

The finding of the significant indirect effect of MBSM on students' characters through teachers' characters proves the importance of schools to manage teachers in order to form good character, therefore to be able to overcome the problem of students' characters diversity in classroom learning. Keskin (2018) argued if management gave opportunities to teachers training in multicultural values at school, this would affect students' character building. The training can improve teachers' personality and social competence (Hanafi et al., 2020). Furthermore, multicultural competence possessed by a teacher, if supported with consistent implementation of multicultural based school management, will give solution to found problems (Raihani, 2018) that multicultural education policy in Indonesia is not forceful as well as teachers' ability in teaching and giving examples about multicultural life is still weak.

MBSM and teachers' characters are important components in shaping students' characters because they have a significant simultaneous effect on students' characters. This research affirms Tanzeh's finding that school successes were determined not only by teachers and principal but also the principal's management skill in improving teachers' morality (Tanzeh, 2019). The teachers' morality here is a character competence possessed by a teacher through effective school management. This management can support to achieve educational purposes in which one of them is building good characters in students' personalities. The good character in students' personalities can build more if the teachers and principal gave them space to implement local wisdom values, a part of multicultural character wealth, at school (Kamisi et al., 2020). Thus MBSM and teachers' characters improve students' characters simultaneously.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the causality test using SEM show that there was a significant effect of the MBSM variable on teachers' characters and students' characters. There is a significant indirect effect through the mediating variable on the relationship between MBSM and students' characters through teachers' characters. Likewise, there is a simultaneously effect of the multicultural-based school management and the teachers' characters on

the students' characters. These results indicate that multicultural-based school management and teachers' characters have a significant effect on students' characters. Likewise, multicultural-based school management is a variable that has a significant effect on both teachers and students' characters. This relationship is not only in the sense of correlation but even more as a causal relationship.

This has theoretical implications that MBSM is an important variable in educational management because by internalizing multicultural values, especially through educational services, increasing teacher knowledge and through the learning curriculum, it involves students' feelings of building positive characters: such as fairness, equality and tolerance to be able to collaborate with other people. This also has practical implications that to improve the character of students, the head of the foundation, school principals and education stakeholders need to provide space for the implementation of MBSM by making educational services effective that can increase the dimensions of teacher knowledge about multicultural values such as multicultural awareness training and learning curricula that more involving the dimensions of students' feelings such as by including the content of local wisdom or culture according to the student's background.

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